

Committing Homicide By Infecting With Coronavirus Infection

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
December 01, 2020

Accepted:
January 24, 2021

Keywords :

Criminal Responsibility,
Vector Of Infection,
Crime, Murder,
Intentional Killing,
Coronavirus Disease
(COVID-19), Poisoning

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5834911

Abstract

This study aims to discuss one of the problematic issues that have recently emerged in the international arena due to the spread of Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic)'s infection which claimed the lives of hundreds of thousands around the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) considered the virus a pandemic and declared public health emergency of international concern, the highest level of alarm under international law.

The aim of the study is the identification of the criminal responsibility for committing homicide via deliberately infecting with the virus; and the limit of the criminal responsibility of the infected patient with novel Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic) about his natural actions such as spitting, sneezing and close contact. The study also searches for the limit of the criminal responsibility of the infected patient's failure to take preventive measures, the methods of proving the causation and scierter between the patient infected with Coronavirus and the result of his actions.

The researcher followed the descriptive analytical method; which describes the phenomenon and analyzes them is that on the occasion of this research. The descriptive analytical method; used in this research to study this criminal phenomenon and applicable terms and conditions. Moreover, for the purposes of enriching the study, I sought out the assistance of the comparative method.

The study dealt with: the human rights to health. Furthermore, it dealt in detail, with the provisions of criminal responsibility and the extent of their applicability to a Coronavirus (COVID-19) patient, and his responsibility for the crime of premeditated murder resulting from the transmission of the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19)'s infection. The study ended with a set of findings and recommendations.

Introduction

On a dime, the world woke up and it was a completely different place, Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has swept the world, hundreds of thousands of lives were claimed and panic prevailed all over the world. Human rights and freedoms have been disrupted, and most of life's activities have been crippled.

Statistics indicate the continuous increase in the spread of the virus, the high number of infected, deaths, and due to the severity and specificity of this disease; many uncharacteristic legal problems have emerged on the scene. Countries all over the world have imposed many health precautions, and in spite of these, we found that many people with the epidemic violate these precautions, and even deliberately socialize with others in order to transmit the infection to them .

The main point in the study revolves around the novelty of the Coronavirus epidemic virus, the speed of its spread, its dangers on the one hand, and that most of the legal legislations are devoid of texts dealing with the crimes of transmitting epidemics and viruses in particular on the other hand. Therefore, the research sought to study the foundations of the criminal liability of the already infected individual in homicide crime.

Methodology :

Authentic Analytical Approach: The researcher used this methodology to analyze texts, rulings and jurisprudential opinions to reach and determine criminal responsibility for transmitting Coronavirus pandemic and linking this responsibility with current criminal laws to come up with a logical explanation for this responsibility in terms of its adaptation and scope.

Comparative Approach: The importance of using this approach lies in comparing the texts of the rules of responsibility for the crime of premeditated murder in the Islamic, and the Egyptian legislation.

Literature review :

1. Definition of Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19)

According to what The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared, "people through direct, indirect (through contaminated objects or surfaces), or close contact with infected people via mouth and nose secretions. These include saliva, respiratory secretions, or secretion droplets. These are released from the mouth or nose

when an infected person coughs, sneezes, speaks or sings, for example. People who are in close contact (within 1 meter) with an infected person can catch COVID-19 when those infectious droplets get into their mouth, nose or eyes).

Whereas, the Coronavirus is one of the viruses that infects humans, causes disease, and affect their public health, which is the cornerstone of the individuals' contribution in production and the progress their nations. Legislation emphasized, in its various texts, the need to protect the human body from diseases in general, meaning that preserving and promoting human health and physical and mental integrity is the ultimate goal of any individual or human community. The physical health of the human being has become a basic requirement since the spread of infectious and other epidemic diseases (such as acquired immunodeficiency disease - known for short as AIDS, hepatitis and finally the Coronavirus (COVID-19 epidemic). Jurisprudence has differed about validity largely over the validity of the criminal law in dealing with such diseases. Since the individual's public health is a fundamental human right, all communities abide by securing essential medical care within the limits of its available financial resources. We will seek to determine a definition of health. Undoubtedly, violating this right is the cornerstone of criminalizing the conduct of transmitting Coronavirus infection from a sick person to a healthy person (Najm, 1999).

2. Coronavirus (COVID - 19) epidemic and the right to protect health.

"Public Health": generally means "the state of relative balance of the body's functions resulting from its adaptation to the surrounding environment factors" (Taha, 2007). The World Health Organization defines it as "a state of complete physical, mental and social safety, not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." In other words: "Public health is defined as "the art and science of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts of society". To define public health in the current era as a good or satisfactory physiological state and a prescription that is given to the life functions in the body's organs if it goes as usual as determined by the natural laws or the homogeneous regular functioning of all the organs of the human body (Rustam, 2003).

Egyptian jurisprudence defines the disease as: "any health Impairment that weakens a person's immune system or his ability to perform his life duties, and the pathological ailment is equal to that, whether it is an incurable permanent ailment, or accidental and curable" (Hosni, 1988). Symptoms of any disease may require certain or special behaviors, such as persistence in treatment, taking certain precautions, or certain types of care and treatment. Perseverance with treatment means avoiding the deterioration of the ailment and the symptoms of the disease, stopping its continuation. Furthermore taking precautions against the epidemics such as Coronavirus COVID-19 disease and increasing awareness among individuals (El-Shazly, 1988). Health care aims also to avoid the dangers that may arise from the normal symptoms, whether it threatens the life of the victim or others socializing with him. Health care represents a set of general precautions recommended by the Centers for Disease Prevention and Control, especially for the workers in health care sites. These precautions aim at minimizing the possibility of exposure of body organs or body fluids to factors that transmit these diseases, at the very least (Al-Werfalli, 2001). Since the current epidemic of Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic), the subject of our study, like many other diseases - is affecting public health, and you can reduce your chances of being infected or spreading it by taking some precautions, health care, and suitable treatment. Any individual causes the transmission of the Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic), or any other epidemics, is subject to be charged by the crime of assaulting the physical integrity, or threatening the health rights or lives of the others, according to the criminal outcome of the infecting others with the disease (Rustam, 2003).

3. Criminal eligibility conditions of a person infected with Coronavirus (COVID-19).

Islamic jurisprudence has established that eligibility is one of the conditions for an individual to be charged with a crime. The eligibility is one of the conditions for the validity of the occurrence of the crime, that is, a condition for the existence of a crime in the first place, and describing the act as a crime according to the Sharia law, so that it has a legal effect, and to be entitled to punishment. As for the positive law, it has been argued that eligibility is a condition of the assignment, that is, a person must be sane when addressed by the criminal rule. It is also a presumed aspect of the material and moral elements, as well as when punishment will be sought if accused. Criminal capacity is limited to the one's right mind person alone, and not to others, so there is no capacity for those who have lost their minds, or for young people under the age of adulthood (Rida, 1964). The context of the research raises a question about an important issue, that is: "Who is the individual is prone to fall under the penalty of law if he spreads the virus? To answer this question, we will list the elements of criminal liability to search for the extent of an infected person's responsibility for criminally spreading the Coronavirus (COVID - 19). Criminal responsibility is established on two components: the capacity to perceive or to feel and the ability to choose. (Rida, 1964).

Without either of them, the individual lies under no responsibility; and therefore it is necessary to distinguish, then perceive and choose. Accordingly, the rational adult infection vector who can distinguish between right and wrong, and is aware of the consequences of transmitting the virus to others, especially vulnerable individuals like the elderly, pregnant women and immunologically compromised, if he deliberately chooses to transmit the virus to others, he is criminally responsible for his behavior and the result of this behavior. This responsibility

shall cease if the behavior occurred precludes the perpetrator's responsibility for his criminal behavior. If the perpetrator is younger than seven years old, insane, has a mental disability, or is in a coma resulting from a non-voluntary state of drunkenness, responsibility for him shall be excluded. Responsibility is also denied in cases of coercion, force majeure, a sudden accident, necessity, and ignorance, and the availability of cases of exclusion of liability is a matter that the case judge can assess by studying and examining the case (Abdel-Al, 2015).

4. Criminal liability for the novel Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic) in the event of failure to take precautionary measures:

All countries of the world have issued many decisions that include precautionary measures to protect their citizens and foreign residents on their lands. The Ministry of Interior in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, on its part, declared on May 5, 2020 AD, that according to the royal instructions, which comes out of concern over the health and safety of the citizens and residents in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and to prevent the spread of the novel Coronavirus (COVID-19 pandemic) in the kingdom, declared the following precautionary measures:

.....

Third: Whoever violates the isolation or quarantine instructions will be punished with a fine not exceeding 200,000 Saudi riyals (only two hundred thousand Saudi riyals only), or imprisonment for a period not exceeding two years, or by both imprisonment and a fine together

Fourth: Whoever deliberately transmits the infection to others shall be punished with a fine not exceeding 500,000 Saudi riyals (only five hundred thousand Saudi riyals only) or imprisonment for a period not exceeding 5 five years, or by both imprisonment and a fine together ...

Eighth: The application of these penalties stipulated in the previous clauses, shall not prejudice any other legal or statutory penalties...

Accordingly, the Kingdom addressed its citizens and residents on its territories and explicitly declared that violating the isolation instructions by the carriers is a capital offense, which the penalty of imprisonment or a fine, or both, will impose for intentionally transmitting the virus. In our opinion, in this article, the legislator does not specify in case of violating these instructions, and intentionally transmitting the virus is it in case of the death of the victim to apply the penalty, or another consequence? In our opinion, the organizer has devoted this article to the penalty for the crime of intentional harm and not intentional death, and it is the closest to logic, especially since the royal decision concluded Article 8 of it by confirming that this punishment does not prejudice any other penalty in Sharia or two systems. The death of the victim cannot be punished by this provision according to the principle of proportionality to the punishment. It is noteworthy that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has amended the regulation on limiting the gatherings that contribute to the outbreak and transmission of the Coronavirus along with the schedule of classification of violations ... and it has stated that

.....

Third: Determining the penalty of intentionally violating the precautionary measures (protocols) which announced on 6 Shawwal 1441 AH, with a fine for the amount of (1000) Saudi riyals, these violations include not using medical masks, or what covers the nose and mouth, the failure to adhere to social distancing, refusing to measure temperature when access to any public or private institutions' buildings. Besides the failure to comply with the required procedures when the temperature is greater than 38 Celsius degree, in the cases stipulated in those precautionary measures (protocols), and the penalty is doubled in case of repetition of these violations.

The Egyptian Prime Minister issued Resolution No. 768 of 2020 AD, regarding translating Egypt's comprehensive plan to protect its citizens from any possible repercussions of the Coronavirus (COVID - 19 pandemic). The Prime Minister also issued a decision instructing workers and frequent visitors to all markets, shops, governmental establishments, private establishments, banks, while inside all means of collective transport, whether public or private, to wear protective masks, "and that the violator will be punished with a fine not exceeding 4000 pounds". It is obvious that the Egyptian legislator and the Saudi legislator have assigned a mandate to all citizens and residents, whether the carrier of Coronavirus or not, to adhere to these precautionary measures and set a criminal sanction for violating the mandate. A fine estimated by the legislator was applied; moreover, the fine will be doubled in case of repeated violation.

Officials in both countries called on all citizens and residents to urgently adhere to the precautionary measures established to protect themselves and their country from the threat of the epidemic.

5. The criminal liability of the intentional carrier of the infection upon the death of the victim

The Egyptian legislator defined criminal responsibility as "the perpetrator's entitlement to the punishment prescribed for it, and this responsibility relates to an offender who has violated the criminal assignment he was charged with, and the penalty prescribed to protect this assignment to be applied to him: (Al-Saifi, 1418 AH).

The elements of voluntary manslaughter in Sharia are based on three basic aspects, which are the same as those of the crime of voluntary manslaughter in the Egyptian Penal Code and other positive laws.

The subject matter of the murder crime:

The crime of murder is based on a presumed condition which is the loss of the soul of a living person, and in practice, if the victim was dead before the perpetrator tries to transmit the virus to him, then the crime does not occur because its subject matter of the crime is absent, and the jurisprudence adds another condition in the field

of murder with epidemics and viruses, which is the absence of the victim of the virus altogether before the perpetrator try to transmit the virus to him (Al-Basha 2004). A case in the point is if a person intentionally transmitted the virus to another person who was already infected with the virus, then, there is no criminal liability lies upon him in this case. The murder was defined in Sharia as the same definition of it in man-made laws: that it is an act of individuals by which a life of another ceases to exist, that is, a human soul is taken away by another human action (Odeh, 1384 AH). Premeditated murder is what associated with the act in which the soul of a human is taken with the intention of killing a human by another one: that is, the act of manslaughter is not sufficient to consider the perpetrator an intentional murderer, but the intention to kill must be present in the delinquents' minds. If the perpetrator did not intend to kill but only deliberately assault, then the act is not voluntary murder, even if it leads to the death of the victim, rather it is almost involuntary murder, as expressed by Sharia jurists, and a beating that led to death in the language of man-made laws explaining (Al-Basha, 2004).

The material element of the crime of intentional homicide:

The material element of the crime consists of 3 elements, namely (the act of assault, the criminal consequence of the death of the victim, and the causal relationship between this act and that outcome).

- (A) **The act of assault:** the act of the perpetrator that results in death (Minister, 1990); In case of a complete crime - or if his act would cause death - the criminal behavior of murder is realized in all forms of life assaults that are committed by the perpetrator, without any consideration on the used crime tool (Nammour, 2002). Hence, it can be said that transmitting viruses and infection to another person is considered a premeditated murder if the virus is sufficient to cause the criminal result; and the vector of infection was determined to bring about the result for the victim. Therefore, this is the case for many epidemics and deadly viruses that have been scientifically proven to be lethal viruses and science has not yet reached an effective treatment for them (Al-Saghir, 1995). Forensic jurisprudence has divided the tools that are used in murder crimes into: lethal means in their own right such as "firearms, poisons... and so on". Non-lethal means in their own right such as "sticks, whips, Sonic and ultrasonic weapons ... etc. The use of a lethal weapon in itself is a piece of irrefutable evidence for the intention of the perpetrator since he has chosen the mean, with his sole discerns, to achieve the result that he seeks about. Using a lethal weapon is a shred of hard evidence for the intention of the perpetrator to commit the crime (Odeh, 1384 AH).

Legal adaptation of using viruses and epidemics in homicide: Criminal jurisprudence went on to say that committing homicide by transmitting viruses is considered as killing by using poison. The legislature or jurisprudence did not specify the type of substances that the perpetrator uses in the crimes as a poison to commit homicide. In this concern, jurisprudence has defined poison in murders as the substances that are given to the victim without his knowledge whether they are taken by mouth, injection, or inhalation. These substances lead to the victim's death through the interaction between the substances inside his body, where the intentions of the vital cells inside his body are destroyed (Sorour, 2003). Accordingly, this definition applies to the case of deliberately transmitting Coronavirus virus infection through rubbing, spitting, or sneezing. Killing with poison does not differ from simple intentional killing "intentional killing" except in terms of the method of committing the crime, which falls within the elements of its material pillar and makes it an aggravating circumstance (Al-Saadi, 2000). Poisoning was a form of intentional killing, but the Egyptian legislator distinguished it from other ordinary forms, by making the means that are used to achieve the result an aggravating circumstance form of a crime. This is due to the treachery and betrayal of this sort of killing, that is unparalleled in other forms of murder. And in this concern, article 233 of the Egyptian Penal Code states that: "Whoever deliberately kills a person with a substance that causes death sooner or later is considered murderer with poison, regardless of the method by which these means were used or given and whatever the consequences of that are". Moreover, the Egyptian legislator using the word substance did not specify the type, shape, or composition of the substance that could lead to killing with poison, and only emphasized its effect, which is "killing and destroying the soul of the victim". The Egyptian legislator stated that: "Whoever kills someone intentionally" (Sorour, 2003). This is the same as what Islamic law jurists have said that killing with poison is: "Every substance that leads to the loss of a person's soul, whether it is eaten or drink, smeared or tangible, and its abuse was through food, drink, injection, or otherwise" (Rida, 1964).

(B) **The criminal outcome:** The criminal outcome in this type of crime is achieved by the loss of the victim's life, it is not sufficient if the perpetrator didn't complete his act fit to cause the death. Rather his act must lead to the death of the victim, and the result may occur immediately after the criminal act or maybe delayed a certain time. The time in which the result is achieved by the death of the victim does not matter as long as the causal relationship between his criminal activity and the loss of the victim's life was established (Al-Hadithi, 2009). The perpetrator may intentionally attempt to transmit the infection to a person whom he knows that his immunity is weak and that the effect of the Coronavirus virus on him may end his life. The perpetrator may conceal his infection so that he cannot be treated, but the Almighty God may sever this bond, and save his life so that the perpetrator does not achieve his goal. So, this case is considered as attempted murder. Egyptian law defines attempted murder in Article 45 of the Penal Code as "the commencement of the execution of an act with the

intent to commit a felony or misdemeanor if it is stopped or fails to effect for reasons beyond the will of the perpetrator.” The attempted murder can take more than one form as follows:

- **A type of incomplete initiation or a suspended crime**, in which the perpetrator comes up with some of the executive actions necessary to complete the crime, but his behavior stops at this point for a reason that has nothing to do with his will. In the application of this type, if a virus carrier, who sees the victim entering the elevator, tries to hurry up to try to spit out on him or sneeze into his face, but the elevator door is closed before he could complete his criminal behavior (Saifi, 1418 A.H.).

- **A type of complete attempt or a failed crime**: an attempt to commit a crime occurs if a criminal has intent to commit a crime and takes a substantial step toward completing the crime, but for reasons not intended by the criminal, the final resulting crime does not occur. The perpetrator spat on the elevator buttons to transmit the infection to his adversary, but the elevator's operator hastened to clean the elevator's buttons, so they failed as a result of his efforts to commit the crime for a reason he had no involvement in (Saifi, 1418 A.H.).

- There is another type of attempted murder, which is an impossible crime. That is when it is impossible to achieve the criminal outcome, either because the executive action that the perpetrator undertook is not valid, or because it is not sufficient, such as the one who tries to transmit the Coronavirus virus to another person but he is not infected with the virus, suffers from another respiratory disease and has the delusion that he had the virus. There is another form of impossibility, which is an absolute impossibility: it is due to the impossibility of the subject matter of the murder crime or the material means used, such as someone trying to transmit the virus to a person who is already infected with it, or to an already dead person, the crime will not be achieved by the perpetrator as a result of that (Al-Saifi, 1418 AH).

(C) Causal relationship: The jurists defined it as the link that links behavior to the result, linking cause to the causer (Wazir, 1990). The causal relationship in the field of transmitting viruses and epidemics to others is defined as the necessary condition for establishing the material element in the crime of intentionally transmitting the Coronavirus virus to others. That is, whenever there is a material causal relationship between the behavior of transmitting this virus and the result of the loss of the victim's soul (Taha, 2007). There is no problem in describing the case if the perpetrator's action led directly to the occurrence of the consequence - namely, the death of the victim as a result of transmitting the infection to him. There is no more need for causation than to attribute the incident to the person of the perpetrator (Nammour, 2002). However, a question arises in the event that other factors interfere with the behavior of the perpetrator to cause the killing in case of (Coronavirus - COVID-19) and affecting the causal relationship between the behavior and the outcome (Al-Hadithi, 2009). However, many theories have emerged about this to study the causal relationship between the behavior and the outcome.

The strongest cause theory: In the application of this theory, the perpetrator's act of murder by transmitting viruses, especially the Coronavirus - COVID-19, is considered to be the cause of the victim's death if the most effective factor in the occurrence of death is infection with the Coronavirus - COVID-19. i.e. it was the strongest cause of all other factors in producing that outcome (Elalfy, 1988)

- **A theory of equal causes**: based on this theory, the perpetrator is responsible for the crime of murder with the Coronavirus virus - COVID-19, as if he inflicts wounds to another by means of a tool contaminated with the virus with the intent to kill him and transmit the virus to him directly through the blood. However, if an accident occurred to the ambulance carrying him to the hospital, which led to the death of the victim, according to the supporters of this theory, had it not been for the wounds inflicted by the perpetrator on the victim, he would not have been transported by ambulance to the hospital and the death would not have occurred (Sorour, 2003).

- **Relevant cause theory**: This theory is based on the premise that the perpetrator's act is a cause of the result if it is by its nature and according to the objective possibilities that it would create it, but if other factors interfere with the perpetrator's act, then those factors are to be considered carefully if they are familiar or unfamiliar (Minister, 1990).

The attitude of the legislations about the relationship of causation: The Egyptian and French criminal legislation did not address - in special texts - the determination of the causal relationship between the perpetrator's acts and the criminal outcome, leaving this issue to the considerations and court rulings (Majali, 1988). The Egyptian Court of Cassation ruled that the causal relationship is a direct material one, and it is morally related to what the perpetrator should have expected from the usual consequences of his action, if he intentionally committed it, or left abandoned insight for the material consequences of his behavior, and the fear that his actions would cause harm to others. Therefore, the responsibility of his murder crime caused by transmitting the virus to the victim can be proved, unless unfamiliar factors intervene and interrupt the causal relationship. Islamic jurisprudence has settled the problematic issue of multiple causal factors supporting the occurrence of the crime as follows: if the victim abused himself or neglected treatment, or allowed a doctor to treat his wounds or perform an operation, and the doctor miscalculated the treatment or made a mistake when

performing a surgical operation, and all this helped to bring about the result, the perpetrator nonetheless shall be held accountable for premeditated murder as long as his act is fatal in itself, or if he alone was involved in causing the result. Also, if the victim is sick, weak, or still young, the perpetrator shall be held accountable for premeditated murder if he strikes or wounded this sick, or weak or young one a blow that may not kill the adult person, as long as this beating or wounding would kill the sick, weak, or young. Accordingly, if the carrier of a virus transmitted the infection intentionally to a sick, young, or aged person that leads to his death, he will be also charged with the crime of premeditated murder, Although this infection may not affect the adult and healthy individuals, and they may cure (A'Ouda 1384 AH).

The criminal intent of the crime of premeditated murder resulting from the transmission of the Coronavirus infection: If the crime is in its essence is a violation of the orders and prohibitions of the lawmaker, then intentional crime constitutes the most extreme degree of this violation. That is because it the extremist degree of disobedience or "*Osian*" as called by Islamic jurisprudence. Therefore there is no criminal liability without disobedience (Al-Saifi, 1418 AH). The jurists have identified the elements of criminal intent as follows:

- (a) **Knowledge:** It means the perpetrator's knowledge of all the elements of the fact that creates the crime. This can be determined by three components.

First: The subject of assault in the crime of premeditated murder is (the living individual). If the perpetrator believes that he has directed his action to a lifeless corpse, then he has no criminal intent (Nammour, 2002).

- **Second:** The perpetrator must be aware of the danger of his action on the victim's life (Al-Majali, 1998). Accordingly, he must be sure that he is spitting or sneezing in the face of a living person, and he must also know that his behavior will lead to the transmission of the new Coronavirus to the victim, and he expects the death of the victim as a result of his action.

(B) **The will to act:** the will is a psychological activity that requires changing the offender's will towards carrying out the criminal activity, and achieving the result of his behavior, which is the loss of the victim's soul (Nomour, 2002). But if his will is not directed towards the occurrence of any aspect of the material elements, then he will not be responsible for the crime of voluntary manslaughter (Sorour, 2003). A case in point, during implementing his act, if the patient adheres to health precautions to limit the transmission of the virus, wears the mask, isolated himself, sterilizes his room, ... and takes other precautions, except that the virus has spread to his wife or one of his children who are living with him at home and has claimed any one of individual's life, the perpetrator can't be charged with premeditated murder.

Forms of criminal intent:

(A) **The direct intent:** the perpetrator's will is directed in a certain way to achieve a result; this form of criminal intent is manifested in the will to disobey. A practical form of this case is that if the perpetrator is sure that he is a carrier of (Coronavirus - COVID-19), that his boss is chronically ill and he insisted on sitting with him, concealed everything about his illness, and continued talking in front of him to transmit the virus to him in revenge from him. He is surely deemed to have committed premeditated murder.

(B) **Probabilistic intent:** which is the perpetrator's perception of the criminal consequences that may result from his behavior, aside from the achievement of the basic result that he aims to achieve from his behavior, and yet he acts indifferently to these additional results that he expected and accepted before committing the criminal behavior (Sorour, 2003). It should be noted that the Egyptian jurisprudence has not taken into account the probable intent in the crimes of intentional murder. In which that leads to mixing of intentional murder with beating that leads to death, and makes the distinction between these two crimes impossible. Some commentators believe that the perpetrator is to be held accountable on the grounds that he was intentional in two cases:

The first: if the law stipulates that.

The Second: If the results are inherent consequences from that act so that it is not assumed that the perpetrator intended the act without intending its results, and with the exception of these two cases, the perpetrator is held accountable in other cases (Abdel-Al, 2015).

The specific intent and the indefinite intent: the intent is considered specific if the perpetrators will tend to achieve the criminal result in a specific physical location itself. To implement that, the direction of the perpetrator's intent to transmit the virus to his wife or brother is specific. As for the indefinite intent, it is: if the perpetrator's will tends to achieve the criminal outcome without specifying the physical location of the crime; accordingly, the carrier person left his home without observing the healthy controls, socializes with his colleagues at work, and with his family, using public transportation in order to transmit the infection to any number as a result of psychological problems he has, here the intention of the perpetrator did not specify a person in himself or even a certain number of people he intends to inflict with the virus.

Simple intent and intent associated with premeditation: the simple intent is the intent in which the perpetrator commits his crime immediately after he decides to commit it without there being a time-lapse that enables him to think quietly before making his criminal decision and to commit it. As for premeditation, Egyptian law defined it in Article 331 of the Penal Code as being: “the intent determined before the act”, which means availability of an element of time-lapse separating the design and implementation in which the offender is allowed to a state of calm and self-control at the time of his thinking about the crime and his determination to it.

The private intent in the crime of intentional homicide: The criminal jurisprudence regarding determining the intent required in the crime of intentional homicide was divided into two directions, the first approach sees that the required intent is the general intent available in the crime of intentional murder, and another direction sees the opposite of that, taking away the victim's soul. The proponents of this trend believe that the special intention is the criterion for differentiating between murder and the crime of beating and wounding, and giving harmful substances that lead to death or permanent disability, for the crime of beating that leads to death in which the law only requires the general criminal intent of compromising the integrity of the victim's body (**El-Batrawi, 1997**). This is in contrast to the crime of murder in which the soul is required to be killed (**Ubaid, 1985**).

As for the tolerant Islamic law's position on this issue: Muslim jurists are divided into two groups, one group that does not require the private intent to kill, and they are the Dhahriya and the Malikis. It was reported that Imam Malik does not stipulate the private intent in the crime of murder, because he does not recognize semi-intentional killing, and he has murder. There are only two types: willful killing and wrongful killing, so whoever commits an act with the intention of assault is considered a murderer even if he did not intend to end the life of the victim, the general intention is sufficient for Imam Malik to form the crime of intentional murder.

Contrary to this opinion, the other group of jurists, including the Hanafi and Shafi'i scholars, claim that murder is of three types: intentional killing, semi-intentional killing, and wrongful killing. Intentional action with the intention of aggression (assault), which is abstracted from the intention to kill, is almost intentional, and if the act is intentionally done without intending the aggression or without intending its result, then it is wrong, and since the intent to kill is an internal matter related to the intent of the perpetrators, they are not satisfied with the intention of killing alone and they saw to infer it from the means used in murder (**Odeh, 1384 AH**).

Conclusion

1. The absence of Egyptian and Saudi legislation from any special laws and regulations that address the legal problems related to the transmission of epidemics and pandemics.
2. If a Coronavirus (COVID-19) patient has the ability to perceive and choose, then he is criminally responsible for transmitting the virus to the others.
3. Violating the precautionary measures and medical precautions are considered a crime in the Egyptian and Saudi Arabia Kingdom laws, and the violator is responsible for violating these measures, whether he is sick or not.
4. Forensic jurisprudence considered viruses as **toxic gems** and that the crime of intentional killing by transmitting the virus is considered as a crime of poisoning, which is one of the aggravating forms of the crime of intentional homicide.
5. The death of a victim as a result of deliberate transmission of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) cannot be adapted according to the supreme decree issued to punish the intentional transmitter of infection with 5 years' imprisonment or a fine of 500 thousand riyals, or both. But that can be adapted according to the crime of intentional harm, not intentional murder, taking into account that the legislation did not specify the result of transmitting the infection and referred everyone who violates this to the legislation in force in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
6. The crime of murder as a result of deliberately transmitting the Coronavirus (COVID-19) from the carrier to the victim, the penalty may reach the penalty for intentional murder in Sharia and law, if its conditions are applied.
7. We recommend that special legislation be enacted, that explicitly criminalizes the transmission of epidemics and pandemics, and specifies the criminal liability on the carrier who intentionally socialized or transmits epidemics in accordance with the general principles of criminal law.
8. We recommend the necessity of spreading awareness about the dangers of epidemics and pandemics among community members, especially the ordinary ones, then the need to adhere to health controls, precautions to preserve the life of society members, observance of public order and the rules and law.
9. We recommend that excessive sentences must be applied to the vector of Coronavirus (COVID-19) deliberately so that we can face cases of unjustified complacency that may claim the lives of innocent people.

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